

The Significance of Time Reversal Invariance of the Quantum Free $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ Part 2

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In Part 1, we suggested that a free particle probability, originating in the desire to have equal product probabilities for any (e_i, e_j) , (p_i, p_j) momentum vectors for an initial (e_1, e_2) , (p_1, p_2) , ultimately leads to the complex unit modulus Lorentz invariant $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ free particle probability. (Details of the derivation of this function are given in Part 1.) We also noted that this complex probability has three interesting properties. First, it is a dynamic probability in the sense that $\exp(-i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ do not have the same value. Thus, this probability can detect the direction of motion in space. The unit modulus indicates that all free particles are on the same footing (just as the classical $P(x) = dx/L$ does), but $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ shows direction through positive and negative values of $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ for p along the x direction. This we argue is important for the idea of interference. Second, there is a characteristic length present in space, namely the wavelength $\hbar/|p|$. These two properties are linked to each other.

In Part 1, we argued that there is another important property, namely invariance under time reversal, i.e. $p \rightarrow -p$ and $x \rightarrow -x$ leaves $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ invariant. We argued that the same $\exp(ipx)$ represents a movie being run forward or backwards. In the forward case, the starting point is linked by $t(\text{initial})$, but in the running of the movie backwards, this point becomes $t(\text{final})$. We argued that there is no time flow when using the probability $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. This allows one to add $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$'s for events at different times as in one dimensional reflection-refraction, discussed in Part 1.

It might seem like a paradox at first to argue that $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ indicates direction of motion and then to state there is no time flow when using $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. We suggest that there is no paradox because $\exp(-i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ are different due to the different momenta, i.e. p and $-p$. Even with time reversal invariance and no sense of time, there is still the sense of momentum in one direction or the other. $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, however, goes further, because p and $-p$ are linked with $\sin(px)$ and $\sin(-px) = -\sin(px)$ and so there can be interference. In other words, the presence of a negative momentum may lead to the diminishing of an "initial" probability term. This is good because if one has events in time, like an initial photon moving towards an n_1 - n_2 junction (index of refraction), then a reflected or refracted photon may be created. If there is no time in the problem (i.e. one uses $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$'s), then one has $A \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ for the incident photon and $B \exp(-i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ for the reflected on the same side of the equation, i.e. in the same range of x values, while $C \exp(i \mathbf{p}_2 \cdot \mathbf{x})$ exists to the left of the n_1 - n_2 junction. The term $B \exp(-i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ may be linked to the diminishing of $A \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ allowing some probability to appear as $C \exp(i \mathbf{p}_2 \cdot \mathbf{x})$. In the case of a single particle elastically scattering from $V(x)$, with $\exp(ipx) + f(\theta)/r \exp(ipr)$, it is the backscattering portion of the second term which interferes with $\exp(ipx)$ to diminish some probability to account for forward terms of $\exp(ipr)/r$. The difference in values of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ is crucial for interference, we argue, but there is still a scenario of no time flow, so one may have $\exp(ipx)$'s representing various different times as argued in Part 1.

Properties of $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$

In Part 1, we tried to provide a derivation of $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. We also noted its key properties:

- (A) $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \neq \exp(-i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$
- (B) There exists a characteristic length, called the wavelength $= \hbar/|p|$
- (C) For $p \rightarrow -p$, $x \rightarrow -x$ $\exp(ipx)$ remains invariant.

Point C implies that $\exp(ipx)$ represents both a film running forwards and backwards. In other words, if an event is linked to $t(\text{initial})$ in the forward run, it is $t(\text{final})$ in the backwards one. Thus, the same point is characterized by both $t(\text{initial})$ and $t(\text{final})$. We conclude that there is no time flow if one uses the probability $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ (or $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$). This is a key idea because it allows one to combine $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ s for events occurring at clearly different times in the same equation as long as one uses $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ probabilities. Two examples discussed in Part 1 are:

A single particle scattering from a potential $V(x)$

$$\exp(ipx) + f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r \quad ((1a))$$

One dimensional reflection-refraction:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ and } A\exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = Cp^2 \exp(ipx) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1b))$$

Because one uses $\exp(ipx)$ s, events existing at different times appear in the same equation, but this does not mean that one can ignore the relative values of p . For example, an incident photon must have a momentum that is minus that of a reflected one. The fact that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are different is key because it means that there can be a diminishing of $\exp(ipx)$ due to:

$$\sin(-px) = -\sin(px) \text{ or even } B \text{ being negative in } ((1b))$$

One may use $\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ probability which means no time present, to have an "initial beam" $\exp(ipx)$ in ((1a)) be diminished by back-scattering terms in $f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r$ to account for the forward scattering terms of $f(\theta) \exp(ipr)/r$ because probability must be conserved.

Why The Modulus of $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$?

In quantum mechanics, one argues that $W^*(x)W(x)$ or $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ represents the classical probability. We note that for a particle with constant p , one may write classically:

$$P(x) dx = dx/L \text{ where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length } ((2))$$

$P(x)$ does not indicate the value of p or v nor does it show its direction nor does it separate events in time. Time is completely removed from ((2)). This is like $\exp(i p x)$, but $\exp(ipx)$ indicates differences for p and $-p$ and allows for interference. The key point of time removal, however, allows one to link $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ to $1/L$ in a consistent manner.

We argue here that it is because both $P(x)=1/L$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are time reversal invariant, i.e. show no signs of the presence of time that they may be associated. It is not simply a math trick that:

$$\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L \quad ((3))$$

((3)) allows one to remove the first two properties (A) and (B) from $\exp(ipx)$ while retaining the third, C, which is time reversal invariance, i.e. removal of time.

This, we argue, is why one may create sums of various $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ s linked to different times and then take the modulus to obtain a classical type probability. The classical probability itself is not linked to any specific time, only to x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we derived a complex free particle probability $\exp(-iEt+i p \cdot r)$ and argued that it had three important properties. First, we noted that it differentiates between direction of motion, i.e. $\exp(ip \cdot r) \neq \exp(-ip \cdot r)$. Secondly, there is a characteristic length wavelength = $\hbar/|p|$. These two features are closely related because $\sin(-px) = -\sin(px)$ meaning that it is phase shifted or reflected about the x axis. This suggests the possibility of cancellation and addition of probability in x .

In Part 1, we strongly stressed the third feature, time reversal invariance of $\exp(ipx)$. This probability remains the same under $p \rightarrow -p$ and $x \rightarrow -x$. This is the same as stating that it has the same value for a movie run forwards and backwards. An initial t in the forward movie is the final t in the backwards movie. In other words, there is no flow of time when one uses $\exp(ipx)$ s. This allows one to write equations with $\exp(ipx)$ s representing events that occur at clearly different times.

At first there might seem to be a paradox between $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$ and time reversal invariance, but we argue in this note, that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ show different relative momenta which must exist even if time is removed. In fact, we argue that it is the possibility of cancellation/addition of probability in such a case (i.e. interference) which allows an incident $\exp(ipx)$ to be diminished to account for probability appearing in another place. As an example, in the case of a single particle scattering elastically from $V(x)$, a potential, one writes: $\exp(ipx) + f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$. Classically, the incident particle should not exist at the same time as the scattered one and so one would not write probabilities for the two in the same equation. With $\exp(ipx)$ s, however, one may do so. In this case, new probability appears as scattered material, but this must ultimately come from the incident probability $\exp(ipx)$, so backscattered terms of $f(\theta)\exp(ipr)/r$ must account for interference which achieves this. (We note that this scattering problem is well-known in the literature and it has been shown that this is the case.)

We suggest that the time reversal invariance of the probability $\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. no time present), in addition to $\exp(ipx) \neq \exp(-ipx)$ allows one to create equations which show $\exp(ipx)$

probability conservation. We then suggest that this probability may be converted to a classical probability through $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x) = \text{sum of the various } \exp(ipx) \text{ in } x$. We argue that this holds because for a constant p particle, $P(x)dx = dx/L$ classically. This result removes all reference to time, just as $\exp(ipx)$ does. $\exp(ipx)$, however, has other features like a wavelength and $\exp(-ipx) \neq \exp(ipx)$ and these must be removed to obtain the classical result, through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, but the time reversal invariance feature (no time) remains, we argue.